

THE EVOLUTION TOWARDS HOLISTIC MARKETING, A SOLUTION FOR ETHICAL CONSUMERISM

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Abstract

Purpose – The aim of this paper is to study the connection between marketing and consumerism and to determine whether the adoption of revolutionary marketing concepts can have as an effect a new style of consumerism: ethical consumerism.

Methodology/approach – The research involved conducting a study on the level of understanding and approach to holistic marketing concepts and their impact on the effect of consumerism but also an analysis of the literature on this topic.

Findings – The paper managed to define holistic marketing, to establish its connection with consumerism, to determine the level of knowledge of Romanian entrepreneurs related to this topic.

Research limitations/implications – *The literature still provides limited information on the subject of holistic marketing and ethycal consumerism*

Practical implications – Once these concepts are adopted, the implications are beneficial for both businesses and society and the environment.

Originality/value – The paper brings to the fore the definition of the latest marketing concept, holistic marketing and establishes its link with ethical consumerism, concepts that once implemented will lead to an improvement in the performance of Romanian enterprises but also to sustainable development and educating the population to a ethical style of consumerism.

Key words: *consumerism, holistic marketing*

Introduction

Contemporary marketing practices are accused of contributing to the creation of a materialistic society based on consumption. Various authors have expressed opinions over or against this statement over time, but no conclusion has yet been reached to prove any of opinions. However, understanding marketing concepts and their evolution, together with their effects on society in general and the consumer in particular, has led to the development of new sustainable ideas and strategies that have positive effects on society and the environment. This new concept, called holistic marketing, can exploit man's natural desire to consume, without these actions having long-term negative effects on consumer satisfaction and satisfaction, on society and the environment.

From marketing to strategic-societal-relational-marketing

Marketing is a complex and complete science and is more than a business process for building relationships and meeting consumer needs, and over time it has received many definitions, one of the simplest being: "Marketing involves customers and managing profitable relationships with them, creating value for customers to collect in return, value from them." (Kotler, 2018)

The father of modern marketing, Philip Kotler, says that marketing should have been written "market-ing", (Kotler, 2016) to remind us that everything starts from a constantly changing market and to understand cutting-edge marketing concepts, we need to understand how the market has evolved over time and with it, the different marketing philosophies. By accepting the compound term "market-ing", the authors of this research give a new meaning to the term "-ing" considering that it refers to the implementation through research, analysis and product design of product-market couples agreed by consumers. (Agache, Izvercian, 2020)

Since the appearance of this concept, marketing has developed around the customer and his needs and even more, around his desire to consume. In the last three centuries, the growing desire to consume and the development of increasingly sophisticated marketing strategies have gone hand in hand (Stearns, 2006) which has led to the development of a negative connotation to both marketing and the concept of consumerism, many authors arguing that marketing and its actions have negative effects on both the consumer and the environment.

Research on this topic is insufficient and no conclusion has yet been reached on whether marketing causes consumerism and whether this is harmful. The aim of this paper is to study the connection between marketing and consumerism and to determine whether the adoption of revolutionary marketing concepts can have as an effect a new style of consumerism: ethical consumerism.

Marketing as a science is evolving with the market and it is important to adapt to it. In the last 100 years, marketing has evolved continuously, being constantly interconnected with the target audience. The rapid evolution of the company's environment has meant that the company's marketing function has to anticipate changes in the environment and plan in the long run a complex approach that takes into account both changes in the environment of which the company is part and in relation with the markets in which it competes. This approach is known as strategic-marketing. (Izvercian, 2002)

The early 90's led us to strategic-societal marketing as a marketing perspective characterized by assuming social, human and environmental responsibility, when the company realizes that between the needs of market participants (customers, consumers, companies) and the needs of this planet can arise serious long-term contradictions. (Bruhn, 1999)

In the continuous development of the environment, society, consumers, values, information technologies, through the evolution of relationships due to social media and new channels and ultra-fast communication, as an effect of uninterrupted access to large amounts of information, a new approach on marketing appears, namely holistic marketing. We propose (Agache et al., 2020), taking into account the evolution of the elements mentioned above and the connection between them, in multi-dynamic systems, the notion of strategic-societal-relational-marketing whose performances become directed both to the internal objectives of the company and to the effects of the company's actions on long term in which all the factors involved in the company's activities participate.

Consumerism – is it a problem or not?

The "consumer age" began when supply exceeded demand. At that moment, the companies realized that all attention must be paid to the customer, to his wishes and needs because he is the secret to the success of any company. Concern for consumer interests is called "consumerism" and according to author Philip Kotler, is not limited to an organizational effort but is more than that, representing "a social movement that seeks to increase the rights and power of the buyer in relation to the seller." (Kotler, 2016)

The problem of consumerism is a very discussed one, having, depending on the authors, two different and often contradictory approaches:

- A positive approach: the consumer must play a decisive role in market developments and market decisions. This approach supports the rights of the consumer by making the market and economic factors that carry out their activities directly responsible for consumer protection by offering tested and high quality products, according to customer requirements. Moreover, these standards have been regulated by law, with various institutions for consumer protection being set up all over the world.

- An approach with a negative connotation, initiated by Vance Pacard: consumerism referring to "high levels of consumption", being associated with an "economic materialism" and selfish and superficial activities to buy products. (Severo, 1996)

With the evolution of the market, the marketing actions of companies have become more influential and increasingly focused on the consumer. Therefore, it is natural that the term consumerism, understood as excessive materialism, to be associated with these increasingly complex marketing activities.

The link between marketing activities and excessive consumerism has created many assumptions, but it has not yet been scientifically proven whether increasing levels of consumption have a direct link with the development of marketing strategies. Empirically one can make the connection between these actions and the increase of consumerism however, marketing activities are not the only ones responsible for these effects. Other factors are also responsible, among which we can mention: human need, consumer desires, demand level, purchasing power, general economic situation, the changing environment, etc. and as long as the total effects of these elements are kept within reasonable limits, the authors consider that the effects of marketing are not harmful to society.

$$E_c = f(M_k, N_e, D, S, M \dots) \leq \text{reasonable};$$

E_c - the effects of consumerism

M_k - marketing activities

N_e - human needs

D - consumer wishes

S - the level of consumer satisfaction

M - changes in the environment

As can be seen, the effect of consumerism depends on both marketing actions, which can be controlled by the company but also on uncontrolled ones such as buyer behavior and changes in the environment, therefore, marketing researchers need to focus more on the effects of science on consumerism and not so much on the effects that depend on consumer psychology.

For these reasons, the question arises of defining this reasonable limit, a limit beyond which the effects of consumerism can have a negative impact on society and the environment.

Research - holistic marketing, a solution for consumerism

The presence in a market saturated with innovative products, advertisements and other customer-oriented actions is difficult for both the company and the consumer who, by its nature, is built to consume. The buyer, who is apparently the holder of a great power, namely the information, ends up being overwhelmed by the multitude of variants, opinions and recommendations in order to make a purchasing decision that satisfies both him and the needs of society. As a result of the multiple possibilities of choice, the competition is ruthless and the companies need a different vision, sustainable and global both on the company and on the market in which they operate. This new marketing philosophy, holistic marketing is an extension of the marketing philosophy that recognizes the complexities of marketing activities, their depth and interdependencies. (Kotler, 2016)

Following the research we propose to define holistic marketing as representing the set of subsystems, endogenous and exogenous to a given entity in which all relationships and connections lead to a system interconnected and integrated with other systems that focus on the "customer" in order to obtain the best solutions.

In the new perspective, holistic marketing is based on research, design, development and implementation of marketing processes and activities interconnected and integrated with other processes for the realization of products and services that satisfy the thesis of the irreducibility of the whole to the sum of its parts.

As a consequence, holistic marketing is a creative and innovative approach that is based on the analysis, organization, planning and control of all resources and activities of a company to meet customer needs in a cost-effective and sustainable manner, taking into account all elements of the

environment and society while creating a continuous and homogeneous link between the company, the external environment and society. (Figure 1)

Figure **Eroare! În document nu există text cu stilul precizat.**1. Representation of Holistic Marketing

Ethical consumerism is a type of consumer activism, which is practiced through the purchase of ethically manufactured products, which supports small producers and local artisans, while protecting animals and the environment, and discourages the purchase and consumption of products that exploits children as workers, are tested on animals or harms the environment.

Our hypothesis (Agache et.al., 2020) is that raising the level of education among entrepreneurs or decision-makers in Romanian companies by offering solutions for the implementation of holistic marketing can lead to ethical consumerism.

To strengthen this hypothesis, we conducted a study on the level of understanding and approach to holistic marketing concepts and their impact on the effect of consumerism, in the form of a questionnaire structured in 32 questions, distributed online to people who are part of our group of interest. The sample is 82 respondents and includes people aged 18-70, with higher education or in the process of completing a higher education cycle. Among the respondents, 82.5percent are decision-makers in the company where they work or entrepreneurs, the difference of 17.5percent being employees or students.

Findings and results of the investigation

The sample investigation relates to:

- The marketing termen, respectively the holistic marketing term
- Marketing practices in the responders companies
- Opinions about holistic marketing
- Sustainability
- The degree of involmment of companies in sustainability actions

The analysis of the questionnaire shows that there is a lack of managerial and marketing culture among the leaders of small and medium enterprises in Romania. The simplistic notions of marketing are not clearly understood, and the approach of more complex concepts, such as those discussed in this paper

confirms the suspicion that among Romanian managers there is a great need for education in this field. This partial conclusion follows from the questions:

- “The term marketing is very often used, what do you think it refers to”, a question with multiple possibilities of answer, to which 46 respondents say that marketing refers only to “sale and promotion of products and services”
- “In the company where you work, marketing means...”, a question with multiple possibilities of answer, to which only 21 respondents associated the marketing function with the product design and manufacturing, 27 also associated with the organization of actions for the benefit of society or with positive impact on the environment, but most said that marketing means creating offers and promotions -59 respondents, market research on consumer needs -60 respondents or the design and implementation of advertisements -59 respondents

However, the theoretical notions are better mastered by Romanian entrepreneurs than practice because in only 4.9percent of the studied companies there is a marketing department and only 14.6percent have a marketing manager. Most Romanian companies put marketing into practice through advertising and promotion through various channels - 24.4percent, sales promotion - 18.3percent and 17.1percent of subjects say that no marketing is practiced at all in the company / institution in of which they are a part.

Figure 2. Importance of marketing function

However, after explaining the concepts of holistic marketing and the effects of adopting this concept, it can be said that the world is permissive, open to the new:

- 65.4percent of respondents say that the fact that marketing changes consumer behavior is a good thing, because companies, through their actions, can educate the consumer.
- 49.4percent of entrepreneurs and decision makers in Romanian SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) do not consider that the implementation of holistic marketing will lead to a decrease in profits of the company where they work, 43percent say they can make a profit, but not as high and only 7.6percent some of them are more pessimistic, considering that sustainable products will no longer be bought by their company's customers.

Holistic marketing is based on sustainability, a concept that respondents know but which the majority (87.3percent of respondents) associates only with environmental protection. Sustainability is a support

for holistic marketing and has been analyzed in terms of social, economic and environmental responsibility:

- When asked about the degree of involvement of ecological actions and environmental protection of the company in which the respondents operate, 11percent of them say they are not involved at all, 41.5percent are rarely involved, 14.6percent are often involved, 20.7percent organize sometimes and 12.2percent often organize such activities
- When asked about the degree of involvement of social responsibility actions of the company in which the respondents work, 12.3percent of them say they are not involved at all, 43.2percent are rarely involved, 22.2percent are often involved, 13.6percent organize sometimes 8.6percent often organize such activities
- 73.8percent of the respondents claim that their company is economically responsible and that they practice fair prices in relation to the purchasing power of the Romanian consumer, 22.2percent cannot express themselves regarding the answer to this question, 2.5percent say that their company could charge slightly lower prices and only 1.3percent say that the prices charged by their company are much too high for the purchasing power of the Romanian consumer

After analyzing the study, one can see an overview of respondents on the subject of marketing, the average consumer can see only the end of this cycle, which is a marketing action. In reality, however, marketing is not an action, but a continuous process from research, design, implementation, realization and feedback as it appears from the notions proposed and discussed above.

Conclusions

Holistic marketing is the one that can give the answer to these "mal compris" in terms of marketing mission in the company's activities and we believe that the implementation of holistic marketing by sustainable companies brings many benefits to the business and at the same time contributes to educating and transforming the market, leading to ethical consumerism.

The duty of researchers in this field is to contribute to the formation of a managerial and marketing culture among Romanian entrepreneurs, to lay the foundations of models to facilitate the implementation of theoretical notions, both to increase the performance of Romanian companies and for sustainable development and education of the population towards an ethical style of consuming.

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